

Community Relations Strategies in the Management of Organisation-Community Crisis: The Nestoil Perspectives

Godsgift Odiepiriye Harold, PhD¹; Benson Reuben Oke, PhD, rpa²; Atawaji Anthony Reuben, PhD³

¹Department of Mass Communication,
Afebabalola University, Nigeria.

²Department of Mass Communication,
Obong University, Nigeria.

³Department of Mass Communication,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Nigeria.

¹obiaz1996@yahoo.com; 08035515351

²okepillar03@yahoo.com; 08023560827

³atawajireuben@gmail.com; 07060714063

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Abstract

In the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, host communities and oil multinationals are frequently embroiled in crises that adversely affect business operations, corporate reputation, and goodwill. When a crisis occurs, usually, different strategies are adopted by the affected business organisations in managing such a situation. As a result, this study examined the community relations strategies employed by Nestoil Plc in managing the 2011 Abuloma community crisis. Guided by two research questions and anchored on stakeholder theory, the study adopted a survey research design using a questionnaire and interview as instruments for data collection. Among other findings, the study ascertained that dialogue with stakeholders, withdrawal from the disputed land and payment of cash as a fine for the desecration of the community shrine were the strategies used by Nestoil Oil Plc in managing the crisis. Additional measures included youth employment, stipends for physically challenged indigenes in the community and infrastructural development, such as internal road

construction in the community. The study concludes that while these strategies contributed to restoring peace, sustained implementation of the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) is essential for long-term trust. It recommends, among others, that Nestoil Plc should consistently and deliberately implement agreed terms with the host community to prevent future crises and negative perceptions about the company.

Keywords: crisis, community relations, dialogue encroachment, stakeholder, engagement.

Introduction

Host communities and oil companies in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria are frequently engulfed in crises that undermine the reputation, corporate image and goodwill of the oil companies in their host communities (Kenan, 2013). In most cases, these crises, as Igben and Ikiyowere (2022) point out, often stem from the perceived differences, misunderstandings, misconceptions, miscommunication and unmet expectations between oil companies and their host communities. In other words, poor or ineffective community relations by oil companies have been identified as a major contributor to such conflicts (Nwagbara & Brown, 2014).

Crisis is an inevitable aspect of human and organisational interaction. Its inevitability necessitates proactive planning and the development of effective communication strategies to mitigate its impact (Itek & Oke, 2013). This means developing communication strategies and processes to influence the outcome of the conflicts to the benefit of the organisation and, when possible, to the organisation's constituents (Wilcox & Cameron, 2006). Organisations willing to prevent crisis must invest in building sustainable relationships with their host communities through deliberate and strategic engagement. There is the need for a continuous positive interrelationship between an organisation and host community (Itek & Oke, 2013; Igben & Ikiyowere, 2022).

Effective community relations go beyond philanthropic gestures; they involve sustained, mutually beneficial interactions that promote trust, cooperation, and development (Lattimore, Baskin, Heiman & Toth, 2007). Organisations that actively engage in community development are more likely to enjoy loyalty, support, and goodwill from host communities (Tamuno-Koko, 2017).

Extant literature has shown that community relations strategies are considered effective and successful when they engage the community members and stakeholders from the host community (Peak, 1998; Nworgu & Odenigbo, 2021). However, Amodu's (2012) study indicated that most of the conflicts between oil companies and host communities had serious implications for both parties because the community relations strategies that oil companies adopted were not adequate in preventing and resolving conflicts in the Niger Delta. The oil industry in Nigeria can only succeed in its relations with host communities if the needs and expectations of the major stakeholders are adequately and effectively

addressed through a partnership approach to development and conflict resolution (Idemudia & Ite, 2006).

In 2011, a crisis erupted between Nestoil Plc and the Abuloma community. This crisis was a fallout of an allegation that Nestoil went beyond the area of landmass allotted to it for her operations and encroached into the community cemetery, thereby desecrating the shrine and culture of the people. Hundreds of women and children took to the streets to protest the company's action with anti-Nestoil songs. This consequently brought a sour relationship between the community and the company. The protesters accused the management of total neglect of the community's development, refusal to create adequate job opportunities for the indigenes and non-implementation of the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) they entered with the community. The youth of the community alleged that the chiefs connived secretly with Nestoil Plc to deny the community her rightful gains with the same old tell-tale songs of bribery and corruption. The persistence of conflicts between oil companies and their host communities has raised serious concerns among researchers with special interest in community relations strategies and crisis management in host communities, especially in the oil-producing areas.

Despite existing studies on community relations strategies, limited empirical attention has been given to how these strategies are applied in real crisis situations (Amodu, 2014; Ukamivi, 2020). This study addresses this gap by examining the strategies adopted by Nestoil Plc., Port Harcourt, in managing the crisis between the company and the Abuloma community.

Statement of the problem

Building strong community relations is critical for organisational stability, particularly during crises. However, Nestoil Plc's operations in the Abuloma community have been marred by conflict since 2007. The 2011 crisis, triggered by allegations of encroachment on community land and desecration of a cemetery, escalated tensions between the company and the community. The community accused the company of total neglect, inadequate job creation, and failure to implement agreed Memoranda of Understanding (MOU). While the crisis was eventually resolved, divergent opinions remain regarding the effectiveness of the strategies employed.

This raises critical questions about whether the adopted strategies truly met the objectives of effective community relations and whether such strategies can be replicated in similar contexts. While some observers argue that the strategies employed did not meet the standards of community relations, which ultimately agree with the Jefkins' Transfer Process that community relations activities ought to move from apathy to interest, from hostility to sympathy, from prejudice to acceptance and, in place of ignorance, knowledge. Others say the assumptions are baseless since the strategies adopted by the company have enabled the organisation to relate well with the community after the crisis. Considering that, the crisis took place in 2011 and both parties have subsequently been at peace, one

may assume that the strategies have been effective. This study therefore evaluates the effectiveness of these strategies in restoring community confidence.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the conduct of the study:

- i. What community relations strategies were most frequently used by Nestoil Plc in managing the 2011 crisis?
- ii. What is the perception of Abuloma community residents regarding these strategies?

Theoretical Framework

This study finds expression in stakeholder theory introduced by Freeman in 1984. The theory proposes that companies produce externalities that affect several parties, both internal and external to the firm. Stakeholder theory posits that organisations must consider the interests and well-being of all stakeholders, including host communities, employees, customers, advocacy organisations, environmentalists, the media, and regulators, among others (Harrison et al., 2015).

These stakeholders are grouped into primary and secondary. The primary stakeholders (employees, investors, customers, suppliers, government and the community or influencers) are those whose actions can be harmful or beneficial to an organisation. Without the continued interaction of primary stakeholders, an organisation would cease to exist. Secondary stakeholders (the media, activist groups and competitors) can affect or be affected by the actions of an organisation. That is, the rights of the parties can either be violated or respected by the organisation (Hartman, 2015).

Stakeholder engagement is essential for organisational survival and success. Effective management of stakeholder relationships fosters trust, loyalty, and mutual benefit. Managing the relationship between an organisation and its various stakeholders is important because what an organisation chooses to do with its stakeholders will ultimately define how those stakeholders will treat the organisation. In the context of this study, the theory underscores the importance of inclusive engagement and responsiveness to community concerns in crisis management.

Literature Review

Community Relations and Crisis Management Strategies

Crisis occurs between organisations and their host communities when one party begins to feel dissatisfied. In the Niger Delta, crisis between International Oil Organisations (IOO) and their host communities erupts when host communities believe that their interests, needs, aspirations and expectations are not given adequate consideration by the

organisations operating in their localities. It also occurs when the activities of the organisations infringe on the rights and mores of the host communities. George (2016) links the causes of crisis to lack of information, lack of resources, personal relationships and incompetent management. Nwachukwu and Usiemure (2021) explain that the nature of relations between multinational oil companies and host communities is critical to the socioeconomic well-being of the host communities and, by extension, Nigeria. It is important, therefore, that multinational oil companies have well-planned community relations programmes and activities which can position the companies as good corporate citizens of the host community. When a company demonstrates interest in the socioeconomic well-being of its host community, such a company enjoys long-term benefits such as community support, loyalty and goodwill from members of the host community. Many organisations run into trouble when this mindset is not captured early in their business plans. The owners and managers of organisations must accept that there is a serious need to intervene or contribute to the socio-economic and physical well-being of the community they operate from.

Unfortunately, host communities in the Niger Delta are still bedevilled with the challenge of environmental hazards, especially oil spills, which have made fish and other aquatic bodies migrate from the region; disappearing forests and species of animals; desecration of community memorials; and encroachment on lands not originally allocated or acquired, among others, due to exploration activities (Igben & Ikiyowere, 2022). This development has stimulated a series of conflicts between oil companies and their host communities (Yakubu, 2017).

As often observed, crises between host communities and oil companies usually start with protest, where community members, especially youth and women, are seen blocking the companies' entrance gates, attacking the companies' vehicles on the road and damaging their property. The lingering crisis between oil companies and host communities is attributed to ineffective community relations of the oil companies (Ukam, 2020). An organisation that wants to secure sustainable goodwill from its host community must practise good community relations (Subi & Amodu, 2014). Community relations shape a company's actions to be socially, culturally and environmentally responsive to the people and places that may be affected by the operations of the firm. In practice, it attempts to solve real and perceived community issues, impacts, and rules in order to increase communication, improve understanding and create stronger relationships with stakeholders. It aims at establishing sustainable goals, programmes and achievements that are community-orientated as well as a symbiotic relationship between an organisation and its host communities (Alikor, 2016; Yakubu, 2017). It involves deliberate and sustained efforts of an organisation aimed at creating goodwill and mutual understanding between the organisation and its host community to have hostility-free operations (Harold, 2019). When this relationship becomes effective, it results in organisational citizenship, where the company is regarded as a corporate citizen of the community.

Community relations programmes must be aggressively carried out in various ways for community members to be involved in. Information needed by the community should be anticipated and provided in a timely, comprehensible and appropriate manner to stimulate effective conflict management among stakeholders and to understand those issues of concern (Yakubu, 2017). Extant literature has suggested that part of the strategies available to oil companies for managing crises with host communities is understanding the drivers of cultural harmony of the host communities. However, Igben and Ikiyowere (2022) explain that the adoption of a given strategy is mainly influenced by the complexity of the problem as well as the capacity variation of the people in conflict.

Adversely, crisis affects organisations' precious time and resources. Fearn-Banks (2002) advises that organisations should watch for prodromes and make attempts to stop a crisis at the early stage before it develops into a full-blown crisis. A series of activities must be designed to minimise the damage related to a crisis (Sommers, 2009). Dramatic and extraordinary intervention is necessary to avoid or repair major damage (George, 2016). In many cases, a crisis may occur because of an error in management's judgement, equipment failure or sabotage from various sources. But the speed with which you recognise, respond and emerge from a crisis can make a critical difference to the long-term success of your organisation (Sommers, 2009).

Some of the oil companies feel that because they have fulfilled their legal obligation to the government of Nigeria, they owe the host communities nothing but charity or philanthropic services. Originally, the concept of philanthropy was considered enough effort to bring goodwill to an organisation, especially corporate entities (Neff 2005). Oil companies argue that having met the necessary financial obligations to the Federal Government of Nigeria, they have no further obligation whatsoever to the host communities. On the contrary, the host communities contend that if not by obligation, in the spirit of good neighbourliness and corporate citizenship, oil companies must plough back some of the immense wealth they make from the host communities' environment for the promotion of their socio-economic and physical well-being. Organisations want to foster positive reactions from their community, but this becomes increasingly difficult in the face of protest from and disagreements with community activists. Thus, for an organisation and its host community to have a mutually beneficial relationship, there is the great need for an effective community relations practice which serves to analyse issues within the community and help understand its makeup and expectations.

Once a crisis occurs, it is important to take a systematic, open approach to dealing with it (Mitroff, Pearson & Pauchant, 2012), which involves a strategic planning process (Preble, 2019). The planning process commences with an organisational and environmental analysis, commonly referred to as a risk assessment. This phase also includes the development of comprehensive plans for prevention, backup, and recovery, along with the necessary documentation. Furthermore, it entails the implementation of these plans and conducting periodic reviews of the overall process. Management of a crisis does not simply

imply the managing of a crisis that has occurred. It involves three strategic measures – the pre-crisis management measures, the crisis management measures and the post-crisis management measures (Nwodu, 2007; Reddi, 2009).

i. Pre-Crisis Management Measures

The pre-crisis management measure is proactive. It involves the cultivation and demonstration of a responsible corporate attitude targeted at maintaining a mutual relationship between an organisation and the various stakeholders it has dealings with as well as putting in place practical mechanisms to handle potential conflicts.

ii. On the Crisis Management Measures

This involves managing a crisis that has already occurred and taking sporadic, largely uncoordinated actions to deal with the crisis. It is a fire brigade and reactive in nature (Nkwocha, 2009).

Crises tend to be less predictable. It can be violent and non-violent. It is a variable or factor which can erupt at any time, be it within and outside. A firm knowledge of its inevitability is crucial in preparing for and managing its occurrence (Guth & Marsh, 2000). Most times, organisations are taken by surprise by its occurrence. Hence, there should be a good crisis communication plan which should include an easy-to-use fact sheet with good background information (Newson, Turk & Kruckeberg, 2010). It is more or less a blueprint detailing what actions an institution should take when they have a crisis. This plan, for example, specifies in detail who will say what as well as various channels through which the organisation can reach out to its publics and stakeholders (Fearn-Bank, 2002).

iii. Post-Crisis Management Measures

A crisis is not over once initial respite has been recorded following the withdrawal of the parties involved from the disagreement (Nwodu, 2007). The post-crisis management measures involve the effort of the organisation to determine the resolution of the crisis, taking stock of the steps that were taken in the resolution of a crisis and measuring the degree of success recorded (Reddi, 2009).

The post-crisis management effort also requires effective communication of the outcome (resolution) of the crisis to inform the organisation's public of the state of affairs regarding the crisis. This communication is fundamental following the fact that once a crisis involving an organisation occurs, public attention is usually drawn to the organisation (Nwanne, 2015).

It is imperative that an organisation embark on well-thought-out research and set out achievable objectives to attain its community relations goals. This has its associated benefits, which include to promote business that provides jobs and competitive wages which can increase the earning power of the local community by constantly inform the community about the company's operation, informing employees and their families about

the company's activities and general development plans, research into what the residents think about the organisation's policies and programmes, establish personal relationships between management and community leaders, support community programmes and provide basic infrastructure, support educational programmes through infrastructural and material assistance, encourage sports and other recreational activities in the community, promote and foster the cultural activities of the community and promote good governance for the maintenance of peace and order, encourage small-scale enterprises, achieve favourable opinions of community members during crises as well as correct misunderstandings where they exist and reply to criticisms and restore confidence by removing any disaffection that may exist among community members (Eruh, 2012).

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design to assess the community relations strategies used by Nestoil Plc in managing the 2011 crisis between the company and the Abuloma community, Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. The population comprised 1,374 residents of the Abuloma community (National Bureau of Statistics, 2026). Using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sampling guideline, a sample size of 370 respondents was selected.

A combination of cluster, systematic, and purposive sampling techniques was employed. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and interviews. The items on the questionnaire were structured using a closed-ended format. Out of 370 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 321 were retrieved and analysed using weighted mean scores and percentages. The interview was conducted with the manager of the Public Relations Department and was analysed and used for discussion.

Data Presentation and Results

Data from the questionnaire were analysed using the weighted mean score (WMS). The weighted mean score was used to analyse the five-point Likert scales. The data for this study were obtained through copies of the questionnaire administered to the study sample and an interview conducted with the manager, public relations. The data presentation was based on the 321 copies of the questionnaires obtained from the respondents and analysed for the study.

Table 1: Community Relations Strategies used by Nestoil Plc in Managing the 2011 Crisis

S/N	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	WMS	Remarks
1.	Convened a meeting for dialogue with stakeholders	181	104	10	24	2	4.36	Accepted

2.	Payment of cash fine for desecration of the community shrine.	157	88	39	30	7	4.20	Accepted
3.	Withdrawal from the encroached land	142	141	12	16	10	4.21	Accepted
4.	Employment of youth into the company	144	125	14	15	23	4.09	Accepted
5.	Payment of monthly salary to 40 physically challenged persons	119	133	19	12	38	3.88	Accepted
6.	Construction of internal roads in the community	138	124	20	15	24	3.98	Accepted
7.	Provision of festive season celebration items to community stakeholders	120	156	10	10	25	4.04	Accepted
8.	Consistent implementation of the MoU	118	158	12	10	23	4.05	Accepted
							4.10	Positive

The data in the table indicate the community relations strategies used by Nestoil Plc to manage the 2011 crisis. The table shows that all the strategies were above the benchmark of 3.0 and consequently accepted.

Table 2: Perception of Abuloma Residents Regarding Nestoil Plc Strategies

S/N	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	WMS	Remarks
1.	The strategies used by Nestoil to manage the 2011 crisis made the company to continue doing business in the community	167	88	39	20	7	4.20	Accepted
2.	The strategies used by Nestoil Plc were credible.	181	104	10	24	2	4.36	Accepted
3.	The strategies used were considered satisfactory by the community	35	40	48	11 0	83	2.43	Rejected
4.	The strategies used by Nestoil Plc were ineffective	35	38	57	13 5	56	2.56	Rejected
5.	The strategies were misleading and diversionary	24	40	56	10 2	99	2.21	Rejected
6.	The strategies used by the company were effective	123	127	34	34	4	4.04	Accepted
							3.30	Positive

The table above presents the mean values reflecting perceptions of the strategies as satisfactory, ineffective, misleading, and diversionary, which were recorded at 2.43, 2.56, and 2.21, respectively. The mean values are below 3.0. However, the overall mean value of 3.30 indicates that the strategies used by Nestoil Plc in the management of the 2011 crisis were effective.

Discussion of Findings

This study assessed the community relations strategies in managing organisational and host community crises: the Nestoil Plc perspectives. A total of 370 respondents, from the Abuloma community and Nestoil Plc, were chosen for the study. The study adopted a combination of cluster, systematic and purposive sampling techniques in reaching the respondents. The study lasted for a period of 3 months. Our study revealed the following major findings.

The Community Relations Strategies used By Nestoil Plc in Managing the 2011 Crisis in the Abuloma Community

The data in Table 1 indicate that Nestoil Plc deployed some community relations strategies in managing the 2011 crisis between the company and the Abuloma community. As evident in the table, out of the 321 respondents sampled, respondents with a mean value of 4.36 stated that the company convened regular meetings for dialogue between the stakeholders of the company and the company's management. It was also shown from the result of the study that the company, as part of strategies in the management of the crisis, withdrew from the land in question and limited itself to the boundary set by the community. This was confirmed by respondents with a mean score of 4.21. The manager of the Public Relations Department of Nestoil Plc, in an interview, also stated that the 2011 crisis was resolved through dialogue which was preceded by the withdrawal of operations from the disputed area by the company. The withdrawal of operations from the disputed portion of land by Nestoil Plc during the 2011 crisis presupposes its understanding of the fact that there could not have been a way to persuade or constrain the community people to listen to the organisation without first identifying and responding to the issues being contended.

Studies have shown that community relations strategies are considered effective and successful when they engage the community members and stakeholders from the host community in a dialogue (Peak, 1998; Nworgu & Odenigbo, 2021). Dialogue played a prominent role in the resolution of crises. Udoudo (2009) states that dialogues are not involved in the discussion of an issue but a careful examination of the issue. He maintains that any resolution that is reached between parties involved in a crisis without functionally tackling the actual cause of the conflict will remain "a mere postponement of the evil day" (p. 172). Udoudo (2009) argues further that functional dialogue demands that those (people, groups, parties, etc.) affected by a particular circumstance should be accorded the space to express themselves, especially since representation by the leadership of such

groups does not produce the desired result, adding that even if the membership of the groups involved in a circumstance were illiterate, they should be given the space to express themselves in their local language through an interpreter. Anticipating and providing information needed by the community in a timely, comprehensible and appropriate manner stimulates effective conflict management among stakeholders. In the face of controversial issues, conflict can be effectively managed when the community is presented with the information needed to understand those issues (Yakubu, 2017). Community relations strategies significantly support the ability of parties to interact peacefully (Anedo 2012). Item 2 in Table 1 indicates that respondents with a mean value of 4.20 stated that among the strategies used by the company was the payment of cash as a fine for the desecration of the community shrine following the alleged encroachment into the community cemetery.

The result of the study equally showed that respondents with a mean score of 4.09 and 3.88, respectively, attested to the fact that the employment of youth into the company as well as the payment of monthly stipends to 40 physically challenged indigenes of the community were among the strategies used by Nestoil Plc in managing the crisis. Other strategies deployed by the company include the construction of internal roads in the community (3.98), provision of festive celebration items to the stakeholders of the community (4.04) and implementation of the MoU (4.05).

Organisations willing to prevent crises with their host community must be intentional about community relations strategies and tactics designed to minimise damage to the image of the organisation. There is the need for a continuous positive interrelationship between an organisation and host community (Itek & Oke, 2013; Igben & Ikiyowere, 2022). The strategies largely describe all activities and programmes put in place by an organisation to foster or promote a suitable business environment or harmony between an organisation and its host communities. It is a planned, active and continuing participation with and within a community to maintain and enhance its environment to the benefit of both the organisation and the community (Lattimore, Baskin, Heiman & Toth, 2007). They are the different initiatives used by organisations, companies and/or businesses to partner with or contribute to the environment/community where they operate (Igben & Timiyan, 2023). However, Amodu's (2012) study indicated that most of the conflicts between oil companies and host communities had serious implications for both parties because the community relations strategies that oil companies adopted were not adequate in preventing and resolving conflicts in the Niger Delta. The oil industry in Nigeria can only succeed in its relations with host communities if the needs and expectations of the major stakeholders are adequately and effectively addressed through a partnership approach to development and conflict resolution (Idemudia and Ite, 2006).

Perception of Residents of the Abuloma community, Port Harcourt, regarding the Community Relations Strategies adopted by Nestoil Plc in Managing the 2011 Crisis

The available data from the study indicate that the respondents had mixed perceptions regarding the community relations strategies adopted by Nestoil Plc in managing the 2011 crisis between the company and the Abuloma community. As clearly shown in Table 2, respondents with a mean value of 4.20 perceived that the strategy used by Nestoil to manage the 2011 crisis enabled the company to continue doing business in the community.

Respondents who perceived the strategies as credible had a mean value of 4.36. Those with a mean score of 2.43 and 2.21 perceived the strategies as satisfactory and diversionary, respectively. However, while respondents with a mean value of 2.56 perceived that the strategies were ineffective, those with a mean value of 4.04 perceived the strategies to be effective. Meanwhile, the manager of the public relations department of Nestoil Plc attested to the fact that the strategies used by the company in managing the 2011 crisis were effective. According to him, the only reason the company remained in business in the community was the measures adopted by the company to manage the crisis. 'If the crisis had not been properly managed, we would not have been here in the community to continue with our business.' The manager assured that the company was poised to continue to do more, especially in the terms of agreement in the MoU and Local Content Act, to consistently gain the trust and confidence of the community.

The results of the study suggest that respondents had mixed perceptions regarding the effectiveness of the strategies used by Nestoil Plc in managing the crisis between the company and the Abuloma community. While some residents of the community viewed the strategies as credible, effective and a reason for the continued operation of the company in the community, others considered the strategies inadequate, unsatisfactory, diversionary and ineffective. The overall mean score (3.30) suggests a generally positive but cautious appraisal. The finding aligns with some previous studies (Ledingham & Bruning, 2000; Nwodu, 2007; Udeze, Okoro & Agbo, 2010), which had shown that crisis is inevitable between an organisation and its host community; when the community feels dissatisfied with the activities of the organisation, it generates different perceptions about the organisation. The reason for the lingering crisis between oil companies and host communities has been attributed to the ineffective community relations practices of the oil companies (Ukam Ivi, 2020). Community relations strategy is deemed effective if the management of companies acknowledges the many approaches its organisation can impact on the local community and the extent of reciprocal dependence; it will help to establish social balance. An organisation that wants to secure sustainable goodwill from its host community must practise good community relations. Community relations shape a company's actions to be socially, culturally and environmentally responsive to the people and places that may be affected by the operations of the firm (Subi & Amodu, 2014).

Conclusion

The study assessed the community relations strategies adopted by Nestoil Plc in managing the 2011 crisis between the company and the Abuloma community, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Also, the study examined the perception of the residents of the Abuloma community regarding the community relations strategies used by the company to manage the crisis. The study highlights that dialogue with stakeholders, withdrawal from the disputed land, payment of cash as a fine for the desecration of the community shrine, employment of youth into the company, welfare support for the vulnerable groups in the community, infrastructure development, and implementation of the MoU were the most effective strategies in resolving the crisis. This reinforces the importance of transparency, respect for community values, and inclusive engagement. It is also evident from the study that while some respondents perceived the strategies as being responsible for the continued business operation of the company in the community, credible and effective, others perceived the strategies as inadequate, diversionary and ineffective.

It is concluded from the study that community relations strategies play a critical role in crisis management between organisations and host communities. Nestoil Plc's approach, particularly dialogue and responsiveness to community concerns, was instrumental in resolving the crisis. However, sustainable peace requires consistent implementation of the agreements and continuous engagement with all community stakeholders.

Recommendations

It is therefore recommended that Nestoil Plc ensure consistent implementation of the MoU agreements. The company should adopt inclusive consultation mechanisms involving all community groups. Future land-related issues should be handled through appropriate legal and community channels to avoid misinterpretation. Continuous stakeholder engagement should be institutionalised to prevent the recurrence of crises.

References

- Adenikan, S. A. (2000). Public relations in transnational corporations: The critical challenges of issues management. In E. Soola (Ed.), *Organizational communications: A book of readings* (pp. 105–122). Delby Concepts.
- Alikor, W. S. (2016). *Dynamics of public relations: A multidimensional approach*. Obindah Printing Press.
- Amodu, L. O. (2012). *Community relations strategies and conflict resolution in the Niger Delta: A study of three major oil companies* [Doctoral dissertation, Covenant University].

- Anedo, O. (2012). China-Africa culture differences in business relations. *Africa Journal of Political Science International Relations*, 6(4), 92–96.
- Esuh, P. (2012). Community relations: Perspectives on corporate social responsibility and responsiveness of government and corporate organization. *Journal of Nigerian Institute of Public Relations*, 2(1), 63–79.
- Fearn-Banks, K. (2002). *Crisis communication: A casebook approach* (2nd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- George, K. (2016). Role of public relations in effective management in Nigeria: An appraisal of political engagement. *Public Relations Journal*, 6, 14–15.
- Guth, D., & Marsh, C. (2000). *Public relations: A values-driven approach*. Pearson Education.
- Harrison, J., Freeman, R., & Abreu, M. (2015). Stakeholder theory as an ethical approach to effective management: Applying the theory to multiple contexts. *Review of Business Management*, 17, 858–869. <https://doi.org/10.7819/rbgn.v17i55.2647>
- Hartman, E. (2015). A strategy for community-driven service learning and community engagement: Fair trade learning. *Michigan Journal of Community Service Learning*, 97–100.
- Harold, G. O. (2019). *Public relations strategies of Nestoil Plc Nigeria in the management of Abuloma crisis of 2011* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Port Harcourt].
- Idemudia, U., & Ite, U. E. (2006). Corporate-community relations in Nigeria's oil industry: Challenges and imperatives. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 13(4), 194–206.
- Igben, H. G. O., & Ikiyowere, T. E. (2022). Community relations strategies of oil companies for conflict management in host communities in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Community and Cooperative Studies*, 10(1), 44–62.
- Igben, H. G. O., & Timiyan, G. (2023). Community relations strategy for curbing conflicts between multi-national oil companies and host communities in Delta State. *International Journal of Community and Cooperative Studies*, 11(1), 38–57.

- Itek, M., & Oke, B. R. (2013). A public relations approach to managing Nigeria's Niger Delta crisis. *Journal of Media, Communication and Languages*, 4, 53–69.
- Kenan, S. (2013). Organisational communication and conflict management. *Journal of Contemporary Management Issues*, 18(2), 103–118.
- Lattimore, D., Baskin, O., Heiman, S. T., Toth, E. L., & Van Leuven, J. K. (2007). *Fundamentals of public relations*. McGraw-Hill.
- Mitroff, I. I., Pearson, C. M., & Pauchant, T. C. (1996). Crisis management and strategic management: The similarities, differences and challenges. In P. Shrivastava (Ed.), *Advances in strategic management* (Vol. 8, pp. 235–260). JAI Press. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S0742-3322\(1996\)10](https://doi.org/10.1108/S0742-3322(1996)10)
- Neff, B. D. (2005). Community relations. In R. L. Heath (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of public relations* (pp. 174–177). Sage Publications.
- Newson, D., Turk, J. V., & Kruckeberg, D. (2010). *This is PR: The realities of public relations* (10th ed.). Wadsworth.
- Nkwocha, J. (2009). *Effective media relations: Issues, strategies and dynamics*. Zoom Lens Publishers.
- Nwanne, B. U. (2015). *Functional public relations*. Delta State University Press.
- Nwodu, L. C. (2007). *Corporate public relations management*. Precision Publishers.
- Nworgu, K., & Odenigbo, N. (2021). An evaluation of the impact of community relations programmes/projects on host community-company relationship. *Journal of Mass Communication & Journalism*, 11(6), 422–432. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2165-7912.1000489> s
- Nwachukwu, J. O., & Usiemure, O. C. (2021). Appraisal of Chevron and host communities relations in Warri South West LGA, Delta, Nigeria, 1997–2013. *International Scholars Journal of Arts and Social Science Research*, 3(4), 33–48.
- Nwagbara, U., & Brown, C. (2014). Communication and conflict management: Towards the rhetoric of integrative communication for sustainability in Nigeria's oil and gas industry. *Economic Insights – Trends and Challenges*, 66(4), 15–23.

- Peak, B. (1998). Community relations. In H. W. Lesly (Ed.), *Lesly's handbook of public relations and communications* (pp. 225–234). NTC Business Books.
- Preble, J. F. (1997). Integrating the crisis management perspective into the strategic management process. *Journal of Management Studies*, 34(5), 769–794. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00070>
- Reddi, S. D. (2009). *Strategic planning for public relations* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Seitel, F. P. (2011). *The practice of public relations* (11th ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Sommers, S. (2009). An adaptive strategy for organizational crisis planning. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 17(1), 84–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5973.2009.00574.x>
- Subi, J. C., & Amodu, L. O. (2014). Oil spillage and environmental preservation: An evaluation of SPDC's community relations activities in Ogoni, Nigeria. *Covenant Journal of Communication*, 2(2), 33–43.
- Tamuno-Koko, F. (2017). *Walking the tight rope: Community relations in practice*. Nigerian Institute of Public Relations.
- Udeze, N., Okoro, S., & Agbo, B. (2010). *Public relations practice: A functional approach*. John Jacob's Classic Publishers.
- Udoudo, A. J. (2009). Managing conflict in the Niger Delta through functional dialogue. In D. Wilson (Ed.), *Communication approaches to peace building in Nigeria* (pp. 165–179). BSM Resources (Nig.).
- Ukam, I. (2020). *Community relations strategies and conflict management: A look at Shell B.P company's antecedents in Ogoni-Land, Nigeria amidst renewed call for oil production*.
- Wilcox, D. L., & Cameron, G. T. (2006). *Public relations strategies and tactics* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- Yakubu, O. H. (2017). *Addressing environmental health problems in Ogoniland through implementation of United Nations Environment Programme recommendations: Environmental management strategies*.